

Soil & crop management

Applied rice research program in northeast Brazil

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Local rice varieties and cultural practices were compared with new varieties and methods under rainfed upland conditions during the 1974 rainy season at three locations in Maranhao and Piaui states, northeastern Brazil. Each plot was 100 sq m (10 m × 10 m); we harvested 64 sq m (8 m × 8 m) for yield data.

At two locations, the rice seed was broadcast; at one location, it was planted in rows. Herbicides (Machete and Stam F-34) were used to control weeds. No insecticides were used except at one location where infestation of ear head bugs was severe.

Results (see table) indicated that:

- 1) the broadcast method of seeding rainfed upland rice was highly successful;
- 2) herbicides gave excellent weed control and were cheaper than hand weeding;

3) the semidwarf varieties IR8 and CICA-4 yielded significantly more than local varieties grown under similar

conditions; 4) the use of fertilizers on the tall local variety Dourado Agulha was not profitable.

Cost of major inputs, and returns per hectare for rainfed upland rice in Maranhao and Piaui states, Brazil.

	Costs and returns (\$/ha) for					
	Seed	Fertilizers	Pesticides	Total inputs	Gross income	Net return
	<i>At Piripiri</i>					
IR8	9.33	139.00	36.00	185.00	877.00	692.00
CICA-4	9.33	86.00	36.00	131.00	585.00	454.00
D. Agulha	9.33	86.00	36.00	131.00	328.00	197.00
D. Agulha	9.33	00.00	36.00	45.00	328.00	283.00
	<i>At Teresina</i>					
IR8	14.00	56.00	36.00	106.00	889.00	783.00
CICA-4	14.00	38.00	36.00	87.00	561.00	474.00
D. Agulha	14.00	38.00	36.00	87.00	202.00	115.00
D. Agulha	14.00	00.00	36.00	50.00	203.00	153.00
	<i>At Santa Ines</i>					
IR8	14.00	56.00	25.00	95.00	636.00	541.00
CICA-4	14.00	38.00	25.00	77.00	546.00	469.00
Sagrimao	14.00	38.00	25.00	77.00	416.00	339.00
Sagrimao	14.00	00.00	25.00	39.00	220.00	181.00

Analysis of yield components in ricefields in the Punjab, India

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The production of food grains in the Punjab - one of the smaller states of India - more than trebled from 1965 to 1975. During this period, rice production increased about five times (from 292,000 to 1,445,000 tons) and yields increased from 1.0 to 2.6 t/ha. The increases were mostly due to the rapid spread of the high-yielding varieties IR8 and Jaya. The varieties now cover more than 90 percent of the rice area. Although these rices can yield more than 10 t/ha under Punjab conditions, average yield is stabilized at 4 t/ha.

Table 1. Analysis of yield components and yield in 47 rice fields in the Punjab during kharif 1975.

Character	Optimum value to obtain 100 quintal per hectare	Values from survey of 47 fields			
		Mean value	Range	Samples with optimum or higher value	
				(no.)	(%)
Hills (no./sq m)	33	22	12 - 41	4	8.5
Ear-bearing tillers (no./sq m)	363	139	70 - 280	-	-
Ear-bearing tillers (no./hill)	11	6.3	2.9- 11.8	1	2.1
Non-ear bearing tillers (no./sq m)	-	13	3 - 40	-	-
Nonear bearing tillers (%)	-	9.3	2.9- 36.4	-	-
Grains/panicle (no.)	103	110	77 - 214	21	44.7
Fully ripened grains (%)	85	82.19	57.2- 96.8	22	46.8
1,000-grain wt (g)	30	28.1	24.0- 32.0	16	34.2
Grain weight (g/sq m)	1000	507.3	220 - 986	-	-
Grain yield (ql/ha)	100	50.73	22.0- 98.6	-	-

To obtain yields of 10 t/ha, we need good management that will enable a square meter of IR8 and Jaya to produce about 363 productive tillers from 33 hills; each tiller should bear 103 fully ripe grains weighing 30 g/1,000 grains. A survey covering a 500-km route across 10 important ricegrowing districts was undertaken during kharif 1975 to assess the efficiency of farmers' management practices to produce yield components. Forty-seven ricefields were studied and analysis of the situation in them compared to optimum requirements is

summarized in the table.

The rice growers failed to establish the optimum number of hills in the field or to produce the required number of ears. The percentage of nonproductive tillers (9.3%) was high. The number of grains per panicle, the percentage of fully ripened grains, and their 1,000-grain weight were optimum in 44.7, 46.8, and 34.2 percent of the cases, respectively. That condition might be due to lower plant population and to a low number of ears per hill. The yield in the fields ranged from 2.2 to 9.9 t/ha, averaging

5.1 t/ha — about half of the yield potential of IR8 and Jaya.

To further increase yield, it is essential that farmers establish the required number of hills in the field (the main limiting factor) and to use good management to obtain optimum magnitudes of the yield components. A regular survey of these factors at district level should be undertaken every year to enable extension workers to formulate sound and better recommendations for farmers.

Rice-based cropping systems

White grub control in an upland rice-corn cropping pattern

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Farmers say that the white grub *Leucopholis irrorata* (Chev.) Scarabaeidae is the principal insect pest of rice and corn in upland areas of Batangas province, Luzon, Philippines. They particularly notice the grubs feeding on the roots of corn seedlings, causing the plants to wilt and eventually die. In certain years, the white grub also damages rice that is planted before corn. Knowledge of the white grub's life cycle provides clues to its control.

White grub has one generation per year beginning at the onset of the rainy season in late April. Adult beetles become active and lay eggs in the wet soil when land preparation ends and rice planting begins (see figure). Corn is planted after rice in October when the third-instar larva is predominant. White grubs are usually noticed at this time. Almost without exception, farmers tolerate the damage. Soil insecticide generally is not used because high rates (2–4 kg a.i./ha) are needed and the cost is high.

We thought that rates could be decreased if insecticides should be applied against the first-instar larvae during the rice crop. In a series of trials, several insecticides were tested on both the rice

Population dynamics of the adult and three larval instars of white grub *Leucopholis irrorata* (Chev.). In a cropping pattern of upland rice followed by corn, cropping systems scientists found that the grubs were most effectively controlled by low applications of a soil insecticide during weeding of the rice crop when they were small and easy to kill. Batangas province, Philippines, 1975.

and corn crops. When incorporated into the soil of the rice crop during normal weed cultivation, lindane at 1 kg a.i./ha provided 100 percent control of the early

instar. Only 48 and 65 percent control resulted from lindane at 1 and 4 kg a.i./ha, respectively, applied against the third-instar in the corn crop.